
FORMATION OF DIALOGICAL TRAINING SKILLS FOR FUTURE BIOLOGISTS

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Abstract

In this article, an exhaustive scientific answer was given to the question of how we form or can implement the speech culture of students, the skills of dialogic learning and the speech culture of students. At the same time, dialogic learning uses the power of conversation in order to maximize the involvement of children in the learning process, expands their ideas and promotes the development of understanding and reading, quick thinking.

Keywords: teacher, dialogic learning, ideas, information gathering, discussion, management study

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Currently, in the era of universal globalization and the rapid development of the flow of information, Higher Education has the goal of training young personnel at a globally competitive level. To this end, the development of comprehensive competence of future biologists is an urgent issue.

In section 4 of the Address of Elbasy N.A.Nazarbayev "Strategy"Kazakhstan-2050" new political course of the established state " "Education and professional skills are the main guidelines of the modern system of education, training and retraining of personnel": "to become a competitive developed state, we must become a country with high literacy. When in the modern world it has become not enough just mass literacy. Our citizens should be ready to constantly master the skills of working on the most advanced equipment and at the most modern production facilities. It is also necessary to pay great attention to the functional literacy of our children, in general, the entire teenage generation. This is very important for our children to be adapted to modernity" [1, p. 6] - the concept pays special attention to comprehensive literacy and knowledge, qualifications of young and future biologists. In this context, we decided to implement through the formation of students' speech culture, dialogic learning skills. The question of how to form or implement a student's speech culture and dialogic learning skills is indisputable to us.

We believe that before starting our research work, it is better to focus on the word "dialogic learning". Studies have shown that the quality of conversation in the classroom contributes to the development or inhibition of cognition and the learning process. Objects and guides that stimulate the process of thinking and learning can be described as "dialogic learning". Dialogic learning originates in Socrates, drawing on long-standing traditional theoretical and

empirical work on the role of narrative in teaching and learning. In recent years, psycholinguists (Holliday, Wells), sociolinguists (Barnes), researchers of the learning process (Mercer, Galton, Alexander), debate experts (Sinclair, Coulthard, Dillon), cognitive and cultural psychologists (Vygotsky, Bruner) and philosophers, including Bakhtin in Russia and Matthew Lipman, founder of philosophy for children in America, created a lot of studying roles.

Dialogic learning is closely related to the most traditional forms of narrative learning, such as mechanical storytelling, interrogation, explanation, and discussion. It's hard to call it a specific strategy, and when you speak correctly, it's a set of strategies that form cognitive/competitive relationships during the lesson. Dialogic learning uses the power of conversation to maximize the involvement of children in the learning process, expands their perceptions and promotes the development of understanding and understanding. Conversation in the classroom does not always give such results, sometimes they interfere with students.

According to Alexandor (2004), dialogical training is based on five basic principles:

- collective: the teacher and students study the assignment together as a group or as a whole class;
- mutual: teacher and students listen to each other, share ideas and consider alternative points of view;
- recruitment: a teacher and a student and, based on their ideas and each other's ideas, combine them into one chain;
- supportive: children clearly express their ideas, freely express their thoughts without fear that something will go wrong; they help each other to reach mutual understanding;
- purpose: teachers plan and regulate the conversation with a specific educational purpose.

Dialogic training is aimed at:

- in what situation is the conversation taking place -in the classroom as a whole, in a small group (under the guidance of a teacher), in a joint group (under the guidance of students), with a student;
- to the objectives of the questions (for example, gathering information, expressing opinions, instructing, managing) and their structure (for example, closed, open, directive, narrow, logical);
- to the objects of answers for example, specific, expert, speculative, offering forecasts, appraiser) and their volumes;
- to the feedback provided to the answers (e.g. evaluator, motivator, diagnostic, neutral);
- how are the answers arranged so that there is progress in the thought process;
- the duration of the exchange of questions and answers;
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- roles and measures in the student-student discussion process;
- to the classroom environment and students' relationships with each other;
- classroom organization;

- lesson planning and structure;
- for an effective exchange of questions and answers, the teacher needs to know the topic well;
- pay special attention to the basic rules necessary for effective dialogic conversation in the classroom (interest, listening, voicing and clear presentation of the conversation, respect for alternative views, etc.).

Biological and other stories

In fact, learning begins with three main types of classroom conversations:

- mechanical (teacher-class): learning techniques and ideas by repetition.
- receiving an oral response (teacher-class or teacher-group): to test previously studied material or to encourage its repetition; deepening knowledge and understanding through questions prepared to guide students in the right direction through gestures in questions;
- give instructions/explanations (teacher-class teacher–group or teacher-student): explain and/or inform the student about what he needs to do and/or explain facts, principles or procedures.

The types of conversation described above are conventional and traditional ways of teaching, which take place in the form of a direct instructional presentation. And the following two approaches are less applicable:

- discussion (teacher-class, teacher-group, student-student): exchange of information and ideas in order to solve problematic issues.
- Using dialogue (teacher-class, teacher-group, teacher-student or Student-Student): achieving a common understanding through a structured and cumulative response and discussion, which reduces the number of options and the likelihood of errors, as well as accelerates the process of interpreting concepts, guides and gestures during work.

We cannot say that these two groups describing the conversation do not exclude each other, but we also do not use mechanical conversation or verbal interrogation, saying that these two types of conversations were used. All five types of stories have their place and meaning. Thus, dialogic conversation is part of the rich oral tools needed to achieve the diverse purpose of the broader curriculum of schools. This is also necessary so that children can improve their level of education, even when they grow up now and in the future and become full-fledged members of society.

Talking can boost a child's self-esteem, both socially and cognitively, so children can:

- for an interview;
- explain;
- give instructions;
- ask different questions;
- for questioning and drafting;
- analyze and solve problems;
- meditate and appreciate;

- must learn to discuss, argue, reason and negotiate.

Moreover, in order for others to do it most rationally, they should:

- listening skills;
- be perceptive to alternative views;
- the ability to think about what they have done;
- Must give others time to think.

The quality of the conversation in the classroom will depend on many factors, in particular: the presence of speech and listening skills in children and teachers (for the development of children's thinking, there must be a clearly formulated map of the directions of thinking), the situation in the classroom, the organization of the class, etc. the following indicators are divided into two groups. The first group is working on a fairly broad topic, which includes dialogic learning. The second group lists a number of key qualities of storytelling that are considered the core of dialogic learning.

Areas defining dialogic learning:

- interaction of the teacher with the student (for example, in the work performed as the whole class under the guidance of the teacher, or in group work), in this case:

Questions are structured on the basis of a conscious answer, the answers, in turn, generate the following questions and are considered as the "building blocks" of the dialogue;

- Individual exchange of dialogues between teacher and student, student and student with brothers;

- There is a balance between social and cognitive goals of conversation, approved presence and structural understanding;

- Not only the teacher, but also students are given the opportunity to ask questions and comment;

- Non-speakers participate by listening, observing, reflecting and assessing the situation;

- The classroom is created in such a way that everyone can see each other and respond to each other;

- Clear, expressive and loud pronunciation is encouraged;

- Children understand that they can make mistakes and believe that such a situation is not shameful, but should learn from it.

- Student-student interaction for example, in joint groups), while children listen attentively to each other; encourage each other's participation in the exchange of ideas; contribute to the discussion; strive for mutual understanding and reaching agreed conclusions, and in this case few people support the same opinion, without neglecting the fact that that there are few of them, but instead respects opinions.

- the teacher's direct control over the student lasts as long as it is necessary to achieve the goal. It provides diagnostic feedback through which children can build their opinion on its basis, striving not to control, but mainly to guide, instruct.

- interrogation (in the course of individual work with the whole class and group or student), which: depends on the plan and content of the lesson; is based on past lessons; reveals evidence of understanding by children; contains answers to closed/narrow and open/debatable/ controversial ("what is it?" and "what can it be?"); integrates the formed routine of daily work and research; uses generalization of information and leading questions; worries about problems and promotes good thinking about them; formulates a balance between management and structure to reduce the need to answer a question of bitterness and the possibility of making mistakes; provides stability in how they perceive concepts (for example, a question is a question, not a guide, and open questions do not involve finding one correct answer).

- answers to questions are characterized by the fact that the question is maximally "immersed" in itself and tries to find the right answer; "Yes/ no" or, based on simple answers, becomes more detailed, more predictable and "thinking out loud", as well as answers are more thoughtful, complete, and not brief and intermittent.

- feedback given to answers, which replaces a monotonous, negative or evasive statement (for example, repetition of the respondent's answer) with informative feedback aimed at something that is being done by the teacher; praise is used to the appropriate extent and is usually used in "rather than to", "Miracle", "Good boy", "good girl", "very good", "excellent", etc. filters out praise; motivates children to express their ideas correctly and clearly, without fear of difficulties if its wording is incorrect.

- a conversation with students that helps children: tell, explain, instruct, ask various questions, think about everything, analyze and solve problematic issues, think, imagine, study and evaluate ideas, argue, argue and negotiate.

A good conversation doesn't happen every time, it has to be stifled. Getting a good answer not only checks the knowledge of the information, but also contributes to the understanding of the child. This approach improves understanding even in pronunciation, reading and writing. The quality of a child's conversation improves significantly if children are given time to think. By conducting a discussion, the student continues to get closer to his goal in his studies.

A story before a written work gives children the opportunity to think, and then write down their thoughts in the form of a sentence. Without completing the tasks for this lesson in writing, changing it to the type of conversation helps to improve the child's writing skills.

Conversation is a powerful tool for increasing the self-confidence of children with special needs and children with low self-esteem. Children enjoy well-structured oral lessons and quickly adapt to its other basic rules, ensuring a continuous course of classes.

Despite the fact that the idea that written work is only "real" work is deeply ingrained, children are beginning to understand that the word itself is important, especially if it is related to written tasks.

Questions: Which approach is most convenient for organizing a group discussion in the classroom?

- What conditions are most convenient for all classroom dialogues?
- How can we ensure discipline and productivity in the course of teamwork (under the guidance of students)? At the same time, which task is better to give? What skills do the participants need? How to develop these skills?

- Dialogic learning involves the requirement "now to me..... who's talking?"and suggests using the most clear questions focused on a particular student. How to find the right balance between the purpose of the question and the requirement for an answer; which of these approaches is better to use?

- What type of interrogation contributes to the understanding of the child? What is the right balance between questioning and explanation? In which case should we ask the student, and in which case should we tell, inform or explain the circumstances to him?

Another way students develop interaction skills,—this is to solve common problems together with the help of affective (emotional) feelings, which two students sum up together. When using the ZHIGSO method, the method of dialogic learning is well implemented. During the dialogue, students made efforts to achieve the expected result, were motivated, shared their thoughts, reasoned, gained knowledge together, replenished their knowledge. The exchange of opinions was carried out through a dialogue between students [2, p. 3].

Thus, the effectiveness of dialogic learning is as follows:

- all students actively participate in classes;
- all students behave freely;
- they don't think they said something wrong [3, p. 57];
- jointly looking for an answer;
- there is a sense of responsibility for each other;
- the lesson will be useful both for reading and for the teacher;
- speech skills are being formed.

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